

Impact of oxygen availability on *Escherichia coli* metabolism to produce 2,3-butanediol from acetate

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ABSTRACT

Many microbial biotechnological processes carried out at industrial scale rely on sugar-based substrates for the production of high-value compounds. However, to support the circular economy and advance toward more sustainable bioprocesses, alternative carbon feedstocks derived from industrial waste streams and renewable sources, are gaining attention. In this study, we explore the use of acetate, a two-carbon organic acid that can be produced from CO₂ or in the pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass, as a non-conventional substrate for the microbial synthesis of 2,3-butanediol (2,3-BDO). 2,3-BDO is a versatile platform chemical with numerous industrial applications, yet its production from acetate has been scarcely investigated. Using *Escherichia coli* W as a host organism, we combined genome-scale metabolic modelling with bioreactor experiments to optimize fermentation conditions under varying levels of oxygen availability. Our results demonstrate that 2,3-BDO production from acetate is strictly growth-associated and highly dependent on oxygen availability due to its reliance on an active TCA cycle. Fed-batch experiments demonstrated full substrate consumption and efficient diol production under optimal conditions. When compared to previous studies, our process achieved the highest 2,3-BDO yields reported from acetate (7 g/L) (up to threefold), highlighting the remarkable capacity of *E. coli* W to produce this alcohol under optimized conditions. These findings pave the way for a sustainable 2,3-BDO production from acetate, providing a scalable strategy for valorising industrial side-streams.

1. Introduction

To circumvent the limitations associated with microbial processes that rely on sugars as carbon sources, which may compete with food resources for human consumption, acetate stands out as a promising alternative carbon source. Acetate can be generated biologically from residues through processes such as anaerobic digestion, reverse methanogenesis, CO and CO₂ gas fermentation by acetogens, and microbial electrosynthesis [1]. In addition, physicochemical pre-treatments of lignocellulosic biomass can produce large amounts of acetate [2]. In nature, a variety of microorganisms—both prokaryotic and eukaryotic—are capable of assimilating and metabolizing acetate under both aerobic and anaerobic conditions. Under aerobic conditions, acetate metabolism primarily relies on the glyoxylate cycle. Acetate should be first uptake and further converted into acetyl-CoA before entering the glyoxylate and TCA cycles that provide energy and the intermediates needed to grow (Fig. S1).

Acetate has been used as a carbon source in *Escherichia coli* and other microorganisms for the production of different compounds such as succinic acid, itanoic acid, mevalonate, isobutanol, glycolate, β -carophyllene, PHAs, acetoin and 2,3-butanediol (2,3-BDO) [3–11], but in some cases the production is still very low to be implemented at industrial scale. This is the case of 2,3-BDO, a four-carbon alcohol that exists in three isomeric forms: *meso*-2,3-BDO (2*R*,3*S*-), *S*-2,3-BDO (*dextro*- or (2*S*,3*S*)-(+)), and *R*-2,3-BDO (*levo*- or (2*R*,3*R*)-(-)). 2,3-BDO holds significant promise in various industries, including the manufacture of printing inks, perfumes, plastics, synthetic rubber, antifreeze agents and fuel additives. Diacetyl, produced through BDO dehydrogenation, is commonly used as a flavouring agent and food additive. Another important derivative is methyl ethyl ketone (MEK), which serves as an effective fuel additive and solvent for resins and lacquers.

Traditionally, 2,3-BDO is produced chemically via the pyrolysis of diacetate. Today, the primary raw material for 2,3-BDO synthesis is butene obtained from cracked petrol derived gases [12].

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On the other hand, a number of microorganisms are able to produce 2,3-BDO, but only some of them as *Klebsiella*, *Enterobacter*, *Bacillus* or *Serratia* are considered of industrial relevance for the production of 2,3-BDO [12,13]. 2,3-BDO is produced from pyruvate and the enzymes involved in its synthesis are: i) α -acetolactate synthase (ALS, EC 4.1.3.18), α -acetolactate decarboxylase (ALDC, EC 4.1.1.5), and butanediol dehydrogenase (BDH, EC 1.1.1.76) also known as acetoin reductase (ACR, EC 1.1.1.4) [14]. ALS catalyses the formation of α -acetolactate from two molecules of pyruvate in the presence of thiamine pyrophosphate (TPP) used as cofactor. α -Acetolactate is decarboxylated to acetoin by ALDC and acetoin is finally reduced to 2,3-BDO by BDH. This last reaction is reversible and 2,3-BDO formation is coupled to the oxidation of NADH. BDH is stereospecific for 2,3-BDO and for this reason, some BDHs produce *meso*-2,3-BDO and others *R*-2,3-BDO [15–18]. One major limitation of the natural producers is that many of them are pathogenic to humans which has driven significant efforts toward developing biotechnological production of 2,3-BDO in heterologous, non-pathogenic host organisms such as *E. coli* [19].

Although the production of 2,3-BDO using glucose as carbon source renders good yields, this is not the case when using acetate as substrate, and only few works have been addressed to improve the production using this alternative substrate [10,11]. Therefore, this study focused on the optimization of the heterologous production of 2,3-BDO in an engineered *E. coli* W, using acetate as substrate in fed-batch fermentations. In silico metabolic models were also used to compare the production of 2,3-BDO using glucose or acetate as substrate, allowing to gain insights into their metabolic pathways. With this strategy we were able to achieve the highest 2,3-BDO production from acetate reported to date.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Strains, media and culture conditions

Bacterial strains (with their respective genotypes), plasmids, and oligonucleotides used in this study are listed in Table I. *E. coli* W and *Klebsiella oxytoca* M5aI were cultured aerobically in Lysogenic Broth (LB) medium containing 10 g/L tryptone, 5 g/L yeast extract, and 10 g/L NaCl (Sambrook & Russell, 2001) at 37 °C on a rotary shaker at 200 rpm (New Brunswick Innova 44/44R). For long time storage strains were kept as 30 % (w/v) glycerol stock at –80 °C. When necessary, kanamycin (Km, 50 mg/L) or gentamicin (Gm, 10 mg/L) were added to the medium.

To produce 2,3-BDO we used M9 2× minimal medium (per litre in

distilled water: 6.98 g of Na₂HPO₄, 3 g of KH₂PO₄, 0.5 g of NaCl, 1 g of NH₄Cl and 0.124 g of MgSO₄ · 7H₂O) adjusted to pH 7 and supplemented with trace elements solution (stock solution, 100×: 1.5 g of nitrilotriacetic acid, 3 g of MgSO₄ · 7H₂O, 0.5 g of MnSO₄ 2H₂O, 1 g of NaCl, 0.1 g of FeSO₄ 7H₂O, 0.18 g of CoSO₄ 7H₂O, 0.1 g of CaCl₂ 2H₂O, 0.18 g of ZnSO₄ 7H₂O, 0.01 g of CuSO₄ 5H₂O, 0.02 g of KAl(SO₄)₂ 12H₂O, 0.01 g of H₃BO₃, 0.01 g of Na₂MoO₄ 2H₂O, 0.025 g of NiCl₂ 6H₂O, and 0.3 mg of Na₂SeO₃ 5H₂O (pH 6.5) per litre of distilled water), 3 g/L of yeast extract, and different amounts of glucose or acetate as carbon source.

2.2. Plasmid construction and recombinant strain generation

Standard molecular biology techniques were carried out by published methods (Sambrook & Russell, 2001). Polymerase Chain Reactions (PCR) were performed in a BioRad thermal cycler, and the different DNA polymerases used, Phusion and Q5, were supplied by New England BioLabs. The oligonucleotides were designed with Geneious software and synthesized by IDT (Integrated DNA Technologies). Restriction endonucleases, as well T4 DNA Ligase, were supplied by New England Biolabs. All the enzymes were used following the indications of their respective commercial companies. Plasmids were purified with a High Pure Plasmid Isolation Kit (Roche) and DNA fragments were purified with a QIAquick PCR Purification Kit (QIAGEN). Transformations of *E. coli* was carried out by using the RbCl method and electroporation [20].

To prepare *E. coli* electrocompetent cells, overnight 10 mL cultures in LB at 37 °C were grown. Cells were collected at 3000 x g for 20 min at 4 °C, washed 3 times with cold miliQ water and resuspended in 300 μ L of cold miliQ water. 100 μ L of cell suspension was mixed with 100 ng of desired plasmid and transferred to a 2 mm gap electroporation cuvette. After a pulse of 25 μ F, 2.5 kV and 200 Ω (Gene Pulser/Pulse Controller (Bio-Rad)), 900 μ L of fresh room temperature LB was added and transferred to a 5 mL round-bottom polypropylene tube and incubated for 1 h at 37 °C at 200 rpm. Different dilutions were plated on LB plus 1.5 % agar medium supplemented with the corresponding antibiotic and cultured overnight at 37 °C.

Generation of 2,3-BDO production plasmid was performed by the amplification from the genomic DNA from *K. oxytoca* M5aI extracted as described [21], the operon *budABC*. The amplification of the operon was carried out by a PCR using the primers BudA Fw *Eco*RI and BudC Rv *Hind*III (Table I). The resulting PCR fragment was integrated in the suicide vector pTOPO (pCRBlunt II-TOPO) (Thermo Fisher) and transformed in *E. coli* DH10B electrocompetent cells. The colonies were

Table I
Strains, plasmids and primers.

Strains	Genotype and/or description	Reference
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> M5aI	Isolated from soil and free of capsular polysaccharides.	DSM 3539
<i>Escherichia coli</i> DH10B	F, <i>mcrA</i> , Δ (<i>mrr hsdRMS-mcrBC</i>), ϕ 80 <i>lacZ</i> Δ M15, Δ <i>lacX74</i> , <i>deoR</i> , <i>recA1</i> , <i>araD139</i> , Δ (<i>ara-leu</i>) 7697, <i>galU</i> , <i>galK</i> , <i>rpsL</i> (SmR), <i>endA1</i> , <i>nupG</i>	Life Technologies
W	Wild type strain	ATCC 9637
Plasmid	Description	Reference
pTOPO (pCRBlunt II-TOPO)	KmR, <i>Plac</i> promoter operator, <i>lacZa-ccdB</i> , pUC origin	Thermo Fisher
pTOPOBud	KmR. pTOPO harbouring <i>budABC</i> operon from <i>K. oxytoca</i> M5aI in a fragment of 3200 bp	This work
pIZ2	GmR. pIZ1016 derivative carrying a modified polylinker. <i>Ptac</i> promoter operator, <i>lacI</i> . pBBR1MCS-5 broad-host range cloning vector.	[41]
pIZ2Bud	GmR. pIZ2 harbouring <i>budABC</i> operon from <i>K. oxytoca</i> M5aI in a fragment of 3200 bp	This work
Primers	Description	Sequence
BudA Fw <i>Eco</i> RI	Amplification of the fragment upstream bud cluster	ccccGAATTCgacctaaggagtaataataatgaatgaaccattctgttgatgctc
BudC Rv <i>Hind</i> III	Amplification of the fragment downstream bud cluster	ccccAAGCTTtagttaataaccatgccgccatcg
Bud Sec1	Sequencing primer	Ggagattctctggataatcaacatc
Bud Sec2	Sequencing primer	gccatgtggaataacggtaacgc

analysed by plasmid extraction using the High Pure Plasmid Purification Kit (Roche), according to the manufacturer's instructions. The correct insertion of the operon was determined by a restriction digestion with the enzymes *EcoRI* and *HindIII*, which liberate the insert, and *SfiI* to differentiate our insert from the rest of plasmids. This process renders the pTOPOBud plasmid which was sequenced using the primers described in Table I to confirm the correct sequence of the *budABC* operon. Plasmid pTOPOBud was digested with *EcoRI* and *HindIII* and the resulting fragment containing the operon *budABC* was ligated using T4 ligase to the plasmid pIZ2 previously digested with *EcoRI* and *HindIII*. The resulting pIZ2Bud plasmid was cloned into *E. coli* W electrocompetent cells to render the strain *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud), to express the operon under the IPTG inducible *Ptac* promoter. The sequence of the pIZ2Bud plasmid was checked again by sequencing using the primers described in Table I.

2.3. Acetoin and 2,3-BDO production assays

E. coli W (pIZ2Bud) was plated from $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ glycerol stock (30 % w/v) in a LB agar plate with the corresponding antibiotic. A pre-culture of the strain was prepared by inoculating a single colony in 10 mL LB medium in 50 mL Erlenmeyer flasks that was cultivated at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on a rotary shaker at 200 rpm overnight. Cells were harvested by centrifugation (4500 xg, 15 min, $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), resuspended in sterile saline solution, and used to inoculate the production media starting at an OD_{600} of 0.1.

The bioreactor production of 2,3-BDO and acetoin has been carried out in a 0.5 L bioreactor (Infors Multifors 2) containing 0.3 L of M9 2× supplemented with 3 g/L of yeast extract and 10 g/L of acetate. The temperature was maintained at $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the pH controlled at 6.8 by adding 2 M NaOH or 2 M HCl. The aerobic conditions were kept by bubbling air at 1 vvm. The culture medium was agitated at different rates from 200 to 800 rpm. All these experiments were performed in the presence of gentamicin (10 mg/L) to maintain the plasmid and the *budABC* operon was induced by adding 0.5 mM of IPTG during mid exponential phase, after 2 h of the culture.

Biomass has been determined by optical density at 600 nm using a spectrophotometer Shimadzu UV mini 1240. The OD_{600} value was transformed in g/L based in the following equation:

$$\text{Biomass (g/L)} = 0.5 \cdot \text{OD}_{600\text{nm}}$$

Yield, selectivity and productivity were calculated as follows:

$$\text{Yield (\%)} = \left(\frac{\text{Diols } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{l}} \right)}{\text{Carbon source } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{l}} \right)} \right) \cdot 100$$

$$\text{Selectivity} = \frac{\text{Diols } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{l}} \right)}{\text{Carbon source consumed } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{l}} \right)}$$

$$\text{Productivity} = \frac{\text{Diols } \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{l}} \right)}{\text{Time (h)}}$$

The concentrations of substrates and products during the fermentation processes were determined by HPLC. In short, samples (1 mL) withdrawn at different sampling points were centrifuged (13,000 rpm, 1 min) (Minispin, Eppendorf) and supernatants filtered by $0.2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ PETC filters (Thermo Fisher) before analysis. Metabolites were determined using Agilent 1200 series HPLC system with a column Aminex HPX-87C (1300 mm × 7.8 mm; 9 μM , Bio-Rad). The mobile phase was 5 mM H_2SO_4 and the column was operated at $70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with 0.4 mL/min flow for 40 min. The injection volume was 15 μL . Detection was performed using the Refractive Index Detector (RID) (G7162A, Agilent 1260 RID). Quantification of all analytes (glucose, acetate, acetoin and *meso*-2,3-

butanediol) was achieved with a 4-point calibration curve for each component, using external reference standards. In this study, the term diols refers to the combined concentrations of acetoin and 2,3-BDO. While acetoin itself is not a diol, it is commonly grouped with 2,3-BDO in the literature because of their interconversion. For this reason, both compounds are considered together when reporting 2,3-BDO production [10,11,22,23].

2.4. Genome-scale flux balance analysis

To explore the metabolic shifts associated with 2,3-BDO production in *E. coli*, we used constraint-based modelling with the genome-scale mode iECW_1372 [24], implemented using COBRApy [25]. Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) was performed under substrate-specific uptake constraints—glucose at -10 mmol/gDCW/h and acetate at -30 mmol/gDCW/h —to reflect experimentally relevant conditions.

To incorporate 2,3-BDO biosynthesis into the *E. coli* model, we manually added the required heterologous reactions and metabolites associated with the engineered pathway, according to the information in the BiGG Models database [26]. Specifically, we introduced reactions catalysed by butanediol dehydrogenase and acetolactate decarboxylase to enable production of 2,3-BDO and acetoin from pyruvate.

In addition, the pyruvate synthase reaction was knocked out in silico, as this reaction—typically active under anaerobic conditions—is not expected to be physiologically relevant under the aerobic or oxygen-limited regimes studied here. Simulations were carried out under three distinct objective functions: (i) maximization of biomass production, (ii) maximization of 2,3-BDO secretion (optimizing its export), and (iii) maximization of 2,3-BDO secretion while constraining biomass production to 75 % of its theoretical maximum. This intermediate growth constraint was selected to explore trade-offs between growth and production without introducing excessive metabolic stress.

In each simulation condition, we quantified not only absolute flux values but also the percentage of total flux directed toward or originating from key metabolic intermediates. This included central metabolites such as pyruvate, acetyl-CoA, ATP, NADH, and NADPH, which play critical roles in energy generation, redox balancing, and precursor supply.

3. Results

3.1. Production of 2,3-BDO in *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud) from glucose

In this work we have analysed the production of 2,3 BDO using the wild type *E. coli* W strain transformed with the plasmid pIZ2Bud, carrying the *budABC* operon from *K. oxytoca* M5aI. To optimize the production of 2,3-BDO in *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud) at bioreactor scale we performed experiments using different agitation speeds, maintaining a constant airflow of 1 vvm, since this parameter is fundamental to the oxygen transfer rate, and oxygen availability in the culture medium, and is known to be a key factor in 2,3-BDO production. Fig. 1A shows how *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud) growth is enhanced by increasing the agitation. The highest biomass concentration was observed at 800 rpm, while at 1000 and 1200 rpm, although the growth rate was initially high, it eventually declined—likely due to a combination of oxidative and mechanical stresses [27–29]. Growth levels at agitation speeds below 800 rpm were lower; however, the highest concentrations of diols were obtained at 200 and 400 rpm (Fig. 1B). Glucose was fully consumed within approximately 24 h when the cultured were agitated at 200, 400 and 800 rpm, but not at 1000 and 1200 rpm which correlates with the growth inhibition observed at these high agitation speeds. The chromatographic analyses performed to identify the products generated in the fermentations showed that as expected *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud) produces in addition to diols some by-products (succinate, lactate, acetate and

Fig. 1. Time course evolution of the experiments performed with *E. coli* W (pIZZ2Bud) in a 0.5 L bioreactor using glucose (40 g/L) as carbon source and different agitation speeds. Biomass (g/L) (A) and diol (g/L) (B) productions and glucose (g/L) (C) consumption are represented. Colours indicate the agitation speeds.

ethanol) under the tested conditions (Fig. S2).

3.2. Production of 2,3-BDO via genome-scale flux analysis: glucose vs acetate

In order to replace glucose by acetate as substrate for 2,3-BDO production, a Flux Balance Analysis (FBA) was used to predict optimal metabolic flux distributions and theoretical maximum yields using both substrates. In this study, FBA was applied to evaluate 2,3-BDO production using glucose (10 mmol/gDW-h) or acetate (30 mmol/gDW-h). We tested *in silico* three different physiological cell states, with three

scenarios analysed: i) maximized biomass synthesis, representing an optimal growth condition; ii) maximized 2,3-BDO production with biomass synthesis fixed at 75 % of its maximum, simulating a realistic condition where product formation is growth-associated; iii) maximized 2,3-BDO production without biomass synthesis, representing a non-growth-associated production phase equivalent to a resting cell state. These simulations were conducted using the genome-scale metabolic model iECW_1372 [24], in which the cloned 2,3-BDO biosynthetic pathway (BudABC) was incorporated. Based on previous studies, several key biochemical requirements have been identified for an efficient 2,3-BDO production: (i) pyruvate availability, (ii) NADH generation, (iii)

Table II

Main reactions for pyruvate synthesis, NADH synthesis, ATP synthesis and consumption, and O₂ consumption, according metabolic model using glucose or acetate as substrates. Three scenarios are simulated: (1) biomass function is maximized, (2) biomass is fixed at 75 %, and (3) 2,3-BDO production is maximized.

	Biomass production		75 % Biomass + 2,3-BDO production		2,3 BDO Production	
	Glucose	Acetate	Glucose	Acetate	Glucose	Acetate
Pyruvate synthesis						
Reaction	D-glucose transport via PEP: Pyr PTS	Malic enzyme (NAD)	D-glucose transport via PEP: Pyr PTS	Malic enzyme (NAD)	D-glucose transport via PEP: Pyr PTS	Malic enzyme (NADP)
Flow (mmol/gDW-h)	10.00	2.16	10.00	5.67	10.00	12.16
NADH synthesis						
Reaction	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	Malate dehydrogenase	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	Malate dehydrogenase	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase	Malate dehydrogenase
Flow (mmol/gDW-h)	16.25	23.68	17.02	21.02	20.00	21.62
ATP synthesis						
Reaction 1	ATP synthase	ATP synthase	ATP synthase	ATP synthase	Phosphoglycerate kinase	ATP synthase
Flow (mmol/gDW-h)	55.8	77.87	38.83	63.83	11.78	21.48
Reaction 2	Phosphoglycerate kinase	Succinyl-CoA synthetase	Phosphoglycerate kinase	Succinyl-CoA synthetase	–	Succinyl-CoA synthetase
Flow (mmol/gDW-h)	16.27	12.01	17.04	11.83	–	11.67
ATP consumption						
Reaction 1	BIOMASS	BIOMASS	BIOMASS	BIOMASS	ATP maintenance requirement	Acetate kinase
Flow (mmol/gDW-h)	–53.18	–41.56	–39.88	–31.17	–3.15	–30
Reaction 2	Phosphofructokinase	Acetate kinase	Phosphofructokinase	Acetate kinase	–	ATP maintenance requirement
Flow (mmol/gDW-h)	–5.752	–30.45	–4.145	–30.34	–	–3.15
O₂ consumption						
Reaction	Cytochrome oxidase bo3	Cytochrome oxidase bo3	Cytochrome oxidase bo3	Cytochrome oxidase bo3	–	Cytochrome oxidase bo3
Flow (mmol/gDW-h)	–17.57	–26.48	–12.10	–22.46	–	–9.59

ATP production and utilization, and (iv) oxygen availability [17]. Accordingly, we analysed the primary metabolic reactions responsible for these processes under each condition and carbon source.

As shown in Table II, pyruvate production from glucose is predicted to occur via glycolysis, specifically through the conversion of phosphoenolpyruvate (PEP) in the final step of the pathway. In contrast, when acetate is used as the carbon source, pyruvate is predicted to be synthesized via the glyoxylate cycle, where malate is converted directly to pyruvate by the malic enzyme (ME) or indirectly via oxaloacetate that is converted firstly into phosphoenolpyruvate by the phosphoenolpyruvate carboxykinase.

The main NADH-producing reactions predictions also vary depending on the carbon source (Table II). With glucose, NADH is primarily generated by glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (G3PDH), a key enzyme in glycolysis. However, when acetate is used as substrate, the predominant source of NADH is the reaction catalysed by malate dehydrogenase (MDH), that transform malate into oxaloacetate.

The ATP synthesis also differs depending on the metabolic condition. In most scenarios, ATP is predicted to be primarily generated via the electron transport chain (ETC), specifically through the activity of ATP synthase. However, under the condition where glucose is utilized and 2,3-BDO production is maximized, a notable shift occurs since ATP is produced only through substrate-level phosphorylation in glycolysis, catalysed by phosphoglycerate kinase (PGK). When acetate is the carbon source, the ATP-producing reaction involves succinyl-CoA synthetase in the TCA cycle.

These metabolic differences are closely tied to oxygen availability. Since acetate metabolism relies heavily on the glyoxylate cycle, TCA cycle and oxidative phosphorylation, it is more dependent on oxygen than glucose metabolism, which can proceed under microaerobic or even anaerobic conditions through fermentation pathways [30].

This has important implications for optimizing oxygen transfer in bioprocesses aimed at maximizing 2,3-BDO production using from acetate or glucose, as further highlighted by the predictions of the metabolic model regarding oxygen utilization (Table II). In all simulated conditions, oxygen entry into the cells occurs exclusively via transport reactions, except in the scenario where glucose is used and 2,3-BDO production is maximized. In this specific case, oxygen is not required at all, indicating that glucose fermentation can support 2,3-BDO production under anaerobic conditions. The oxygen demand also varies significantly across the different scenarios. The highest oxygen requirement is observed under acetate-fed, growth-associated conditions, due to the dependency of acetate metabolism on the glyoxylate cycle, TCA cycle and oxidative phosphorylation. In contrast, glucose metabolism only required oxygen in growth conditions but less amount than acetate metabolism. Under non-growth or limited-growth conditions, metabolism relies more heavily on fermentative pathways, which can operate with minimal or no oxygen input.

Another key aspect is the distribution of ATP consumption under different conditions (Table II). Regardless of the carbon source simulated, when biomass growth is allowed (either full or 75 % of the maximum), the majority of ATP is directed toward biomass synthesis. However, secondary ATP-consuming reactions differ depending on the substrate. In glucose metabolism, additional ATP is consumed during glycolysis, particularly in the reaction catalysed by phosphofructokinase. In acetate metabolism, the main secondary ATP sink is the reaction catalysed by acetate kinase, involved in acetate activation. While both substrates require ATP for their uptake, glucose metabolism allows for net ATP generation through substrate-level phosphorylation. Glycolysis yields four ATP molecules per glucose molecule. On the other hand, acetate metabolism consumes ATP during its initial activation and relies entirely on the glyoxylate cycle, TCA cycle and oxidative phosphorylation for ATP generation, making it more energy-intensive and oxygen-dependent. These observations reinforce the notion that glucose offers an energetically more favourable and oxygen-independent pathway for 2,3-BDO production than acetate.

3.3. 2,3-BDO production from acetate in batch condition

Based on the model predictions, we conducted a set of experiments to validate the oxygen dependency of 2,3-BDO production from acetate using *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud). Specifically, we varied the agitation speed from 200 to 1200 rpm in bioreactor cultures to modulate oxygen availability, maintaining a constant airflow of 1 vvm (Fig. 2). As expected, biomass growth was strongly dependent on oxygen supply. The highest biomass concentration was achieved at 800 rpm (Fig. 2A), suggesting optimal oxygen availability for growth at this agitation level. In contrast, the lowest biomass levels were observed at 200 rpm, likely due to oxygen limitation, and at 1200 rpm, where excessive agitation likely led to growth inhibition as observed in the experiments performed with glucose. Interestingly, the highest concentration of 2,3-BDO was observed at 1000 rpm (Fig. 2B). The acetate consumption profiles further support these findings (Fig. 2C), since the complete acetate utilization occurred at 600, 800, and 1000 rpm, while minimal substrate uptake was observed at 200 rpm, again emphasizing the role of oxidative metabolism in acetate assimilation. A minimal substrate uptake was also observed at 1200 rpm where a growth inhibition takes place due most probably to high mechanical and oxidative stresses. Analysis of the dissolved oxygen (DO) profiles across agitation conditions (Fig. S3) confirms the distinct physiological responses observed: oxygen limitation occurs at 200, 400, and 600 rpm, whereas at 1200 rpm the absence of oxygen limitation, combined with the elevated shear environment, is consistent with a hydrodynamic stress.

Fig. 3 compares 2,3-BDO titres and yields in the glucose and acetate bioreactors with different agitation speeds. Notably, the optimal conditions for each substrate are markedly different: 400 rpm for glucose and 1000 rpm for acetate. This different behaviour is clearly illustrated in both the final titers (Fig. 3A) and yields (Fig. 3B). As agitation increases, the yield of 2,3-BDO from acetate improves, whereas it declines for glucose. These results underscore the contrasting oxygen requirements of fermentative glucose metabolism versus oxidative acetate metabolism.

A very interesting result observed in the HPLC chromatograms of these analyses is that by-products were not observed in fermentations with acetate (Fig. S2), the bacteria under these conditions do not secrete lactate, ethanol, or succinate in significant amounts.

3.4. 2,3-BDO production from acetate in fed batch conditions

Once the optimal agitation conditions for 2,3-BDO production were established, a fed-batch experiment was carried out using acetate as the sole carbon source. In this setup, three acetate feeds were administered (initial feed +2 subsequent additions), being acetate completely consumed in each case. In a parallel experiment, a similar fed-batch strategy was implemented, but the acetate feed was supplemented with yeast extract (YE) at a concentration of 3 g/L. Fig. 4 shows that in the absence of YE, biomass growth ceased after 30 h. Interestingly, under these conditions, 2,3-BDO production also ceases, despite continued acetate consumption. These findings strongly suggest that 2,3-BDO production from acetate is growth-associated. In the case of the fermentation without YE, the maximum production of diols was 3 g/L at 30 h, while in the bioreactor with YE the production increased to 7 g/L at 72 h.

4. Discussion

Microbial production of 2,3-butanediol (2,3-BDO) has largely focused on glucose-based fermentations using wild-type strains of organisms such as *Enterobacter* and *Klebsiella* [17]. A major bottleneck in these systems is the formation of by-products that reduce overall yields in the production of 2,3-BDO, another overflow metabolite. To address this problem, many groups have engineered strains with deletions in key by-product pathways (e.g., $\Delta ldhA$, $\Delta adhE$, Δpta , $\Delta frdA$), achieving

Fig. 2. Time course evolution of the experiments performed with *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud) in 0.5 L bioreactor using acetate (10 g/L) as carbon source and different agitations speeds. Biomass (g/L) (A) and diol (g/L) (B) production and acetate (g/L) (C) consumption are represented. Colours indicate the agitation speeds.

Fig. 3. Diol titer (A) and yield (B) calculated from the experiments with glucose (40 g/L) (green circles) and acetate (10 g/L) (purple squares) at different agitation speeds in 0.5 L bioreactor experiments using *E. coli* W (pIZ2Bud).

substantial increases in 2,3-BDO titres [31–34]. Furthermore, such mutants have also been engineered to produce 2,3-BDO from substrates other than glucose, and in this sense, Novak et al. (2020) employed an *E. coli* W $\Delta 4$ strain ($\Delta dhA \Delta adhE \Delta pta \Delta frdA$) harbouring the *budABC* operon from *Enterobacter cloacae* subsp. *dissolvens* to produce 2,3-BDO from acetate, reporting higher yields using the mutant compared to the wild-type W strain [10]. However, our chromatographic analyses indicate that when the cells are cultured using acetate as carbon source under optimized conditions *E. coli* does not secrete by-products and therefore, the ΔdhA , $\Delta adhE$, Δpta , and $\Delta frdA$ deletions are not necessary to increase the production of 2,3-BDO. In fact these authors showed that the Δpta , (phosphate acetyl transferase) and $\Delta frdA$ (fumarate reductase) deletions does not influence the production of 2,3-BDO from acetate [10].

On the other hand, oxygen supply critically influences 2,3-BDO production because diols synthesis (acetoin and 2,3-BDO) depends on the intracellular redox balance, specifically the NADH/NAD⁺ ratio [16,35]. Accordingly, many studies on glucose-based fermentations have optimized oxygen transfer. For example, Xu et al. (2014) found that 400 rpm agitation maximized 2,3-BDO titers in *E. coli* [36]. Other studies also suggest the idea that the production of 2,3-BDO requires a medium oxygen supply (midpoint) using glucose as substrate [37]. Such results reinforce our finding that 400 rpm is optimal for glucose-derived 2,3-BDO in *E. coli* W.

However, there are no studies on the influence of oxygen on fermentation to produce 2,3-BDO from acetate. In fact, there are only two reports in the literature where diols are produced from acetate [10,11]. In addition, very few studies have been carried out to determine the relationships between the metabolism of acetate and oxygen supply in *E. coli*. In this sense, Phue and Shiloach (2005) [30] examined how dissolved-oxygen (DO) concentration affects acetate accumulation in *E. coli* BL21, showing that lower DO led to higher acetate titres and to a moderated expression of genes involved in acetate metabolism. However, they did not address the effect on acetate uptake or downstream product formation. This highlights the need for dedicated studies on oxygen's role in acetate valorisation pathways, especially given the growing interest in repurposing acetate as a sustainable feedstock.

Our FBA predictions and bioreactor experiments fill this gap by demonstrating that efficient 2,3-BDO production from acetate requires high oxygen transfer. Specifically, an agitation rate of 1000 rpm proved optimal for maximizing 2,3-BDO production from acetate. At this level, oxygen availability is sufficient to sustain acetate metabolism via both the TCA and glyoxylate cycles without causing growth inhibition. In contrast, 2,3-BDO production from glucose does not require such high oxygen levels, as previously discussed. This observation highlights the fundamental metabolic differences between these two carbon sources,

Fig. 4. Fed-Batch experiments performed at 1000 rpm using acetate as substrate. A) Biomass evolution; B) Diols concentration; and C) Acetate consumption. The different experiments represented in the graphs are carried out adding acetate (10 g/L) and yeast extract (3 g/L) in each fed (purple lines) and only with acetate (10 g/L) (green lines). Experiments were performed in a 1 L bioreactor at 30 °C.

confirming that oxygen availability is critical for maximizing 2,3-BDO production from acetate. Unlike glucose assimilation—which can progress under microaerobic or even anaerobic conditions—acetate assimilation relies on the TCA cycle and oxidative phosphorylation, processes that are strictly oxygen-dependent. The synthesis of acetyl-CoA requires ATP that is mainly provided by the oxidative phosphorylation. In contrast, glucose metabolism produces pyruvate directly through glycolysis, along with ATP and NADH without the need for oxygen. In addition, acetate must be metabolized through the glyoxylate cycle to provide pyruvate and the intermediates needed to grow.

Mass and energy balances (shown below) further reveal the marked differences in metabolic efficiency between glucose and acetate. Through glycolysis it is possible to obtain one molecule of 2,3-BDO from one glucose molecule by losing two carbon atoms as CO₂. This process renders 2 pyruvate molecules that are converted into acetoin, 2 ATP and 2 NADH molecules, but one NADH is used to reduce acetoin to 2,3-BDO. Therefore, the glucose balance to render 2,3-BDO is:

In contrast, in the acetate metabolism the two pyruvate molecules that are required to create 2,3-BDO are generated by four molecules of acetyl-CoA through the glyoxylate cycle that also renders 2 NADH molecules. One of these NADH molecules is used to reduce acetoin to 2–3 BDO whereas the other is used to produce the ATP required to synthesize acetyl-CoA from acetate. However, this additional NADH can only generate about 2.5 ATP molecules through the electron transport chain using molecular oxygen, whereas the process requires 4 ATP molecules to generate the starting 4 acetyl-CoA molecules. Therefore, additional NADH molecules must be generated through the glyoxylate or the TCA cycles. However, when cells are consuming acetate as the only carbon source the TCA cycle is only partially functional because it does not retain carbon to grow (carbon is retained only through the glyoxylate cycle) and thus, TCA works only to provide energy. Therefore, at least one additional acetate molecule in the case of using the TCA cycle and two acetate molecules in the case of using the glyoxylate cycle must be consumed in order to produce the additional ATP required to generate enough acetyl-CoA. Therefore, a simplified balance only considering acetate and 2,3-BDO can be:

Therefore, the transformation of acetate in 2,3-BDO totally depends

on the transformation of NADH into ATP through the electron transport chain, which requires molecular oxygen. Several studies have shown that oxygen limitation leads to constitutive repression of the glyoxylate cycle [30], highlighting the strong dependency of 2,3-BDO production from acetate on oxygen availability. This is, although the glyoxylate cycle and the TCA cycle do not use oxygen, the NADH or FADH₂ produced through the cycles have to be transformed into ATP to uptake the acetate and to obtain energy to grow by the electron transport chain that requires oxygen. Similarly, nitrogen availability is also essential for the regulation of this metabolic pathway, since the activity of TCA cycle required to assimilate nitrogen is modulated by nitrogen levels through oxoglutarate [38]. This can explain why 2,3-BDO production from acetate requires at least a partially active TCA cycle, which in turn depends not only on sufficient oxygen but also on the presence of nitrogen in the medium [39].

Fed-batch experiments (Fig. 4) suggest that 2,3-BDO production is growth-associated and potentially dependent on nitrogen availability in the medium. In this sense, the presence of YE in the medium increases bacterial biomass and 2,3-BDO production. Different carbon and nitrogen sources, vitamins, and many other cofactors in the YE contributes to increase the growth when acetate is used as the main carbon and energy source. Nevertheless, although additional research is required to elucidate their specific contribution Novack et al. [10] have shown that it is possible to increase the diol production when using acetate as carbon source replacing YE by adding vitamins and aspartate to the medium that gave cultures a start-kick.

Regarding the dissolved oxygen (DO) profiles, a limitation in oxygen availability can be observed under agitation rates of 200, 400, and 600 rpm (Fig. S3 A–C). At a certain point, the DO concentration drops to zero, indicating that the oxygen transfer rate (OTR) equals the oxygen uptake rate (OUR). In contrast, at 1200 rpm (Fig. S3 F) no oxygen transfer limitation is observed; in this case, the OTR consistently exceeds the OUR throughout the process.

A clear decrease in both biomass and BDO production was observed when the stirring speed increased from 1000 to 1200 rpm (Fig. 2). This decline can be primarily attributed to the intensification of shear forces and the resulting hydrodynamic stress within the bioreactor. Such high agitation rates can compromise cell integrity, reduce viability, and disrupt metabolic activity. These effects have been widely documented in stirred tank bioreactors (STRs), where stirring speed is considered the main driver of mechanical stress, especially in bacterial cultures [40].

All the findings discussed above culminate in achieving the highest 2,3-BDO production yields from acetate reported to date (7 g/L). As far

as we know, only two other studies have explored 2,3-BDO production in *E. coli* from acetate, both with significantly lower performance. Novak et al. (2020) employed a genetically engineered *E. coli* W strain, in which the formation of lactate, ethanol, succinate and acetate were eliminated in order to increase the 2,3-BDO yield [10]. Moreover, they showed that aspartate addition to the medium was required to achieve an optimal production [10]. Ricci et al. (2025) [11] engineered *E. coli* W over-expressing the genes for acetate consumption (*ackA*, *pta* and *maeA*), but still the 2,3-BDO production was low. Interestingly, our results were achieved using a wild-type *E. coli* W strain, without any genetic modifications aimed at blocking competing pathways or enhancing acetate assimilation. Our approach relied on a deep understanding of cellular metabolism and a rational process design. Therefore, our work highlights the potential of non-engineered strains when fermentation conditions are optimized.

5. Conclusions

The combination of a bioprocess optimization strategy in reactors with in silico modelling of the process provide new insights for optimizing acetate-based 2,3-BDO production and highlight the importance of balancing nutrient and oxygen availability to sustain metabolic activity and product formation using this substrate as feedstock. Notably, this study reports the highest yields achieved to date for 2,3-BDO production from acetate (7 g/L). Importantly, these results were obtained using *E. coli* W wild type strain as host, showing that genetic modifications to eliminate by product formation is not required under optimized bioprocess conditions, demonstrating the inherent potential of this strain to produce 2,3-BDO and other metabolites from acetate.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Irene Cano: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Isabel de la Torre:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jaime Muñoz-Triviño:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Miguel G. Acedos:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jorge Barriuso:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **José L. García:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.169016>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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